

Survey the Impact of Rector's Humble Leadership Behavior on University Performance by mediating role of Top Management Teams' [TMT] TransactiveMemory System- Case study: university of Georgia, Tbilisi.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to Survey the impact of Rector's humble leadership behavior on university performance by mediating the role of TMTs transactive memory system. The present study is an applied research and in terms of method is also descriptive-survey. The statistical population of this research is 250 professors of the University of Georgia in Tbilisi and the sample size is 148 according to Morgan table In this study, the required data were collected using a standard 15-item questionnaire. CVR test was used for validity and Cronbach's alpha method was used for reliability. Then k-s test as well as structural equations and path analysis with SMART PLS software were used. The results showed Rector's humble leadership behavior has not a positive impact on TMT's transactive memory system and university performance but TMTs' transactive memory system has a positive impact on university performance and as a result: we proved that by mediating the role of Top Management Team (TMT's transactive memory system) Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance.

Introduction

Moghimi and Dastouri (2021) studied the application of CRM [Customer Relationship Management] at universities in Georgia and mentioned the importance of student's satisfaction and their durable relationship with universities. Humility is one of the fundamental virtues that has been mentioned in most philosophical, religious and scientific texts and recently gained a special place in the studies of organizations and management. This study has been conducted to understand the concept of humility in the content of the organization and management (Mohammadian et al., 2018). Humility is a virtue that almost all managers have enjoyed or practiced. A review of world-renowned magazines shows that the virtue of humility and humbleness has grown significantly since 2014, and in the meantime, the traces of this concept entering the content of the organization, management, leadership and business are interesting. On the other hand, the roots of recent organizational scandals are attributed to the unbridled self, arrogance, sense of righteousness and arrogance of managers (Rego et al., 2016). The virtue of humility has attracted a great deal of interest and is an important characteristic of managers who want to lead modern-day businesses or work in these organizations. According to theorists, humility is becoming a vital issue for leaders who want to lead their organizations in a dynamic and chaotic environment in the face of the unpredictability and ignorance that businessmen face, and the expansion of personalities. Their utilitarian actions develop a perception of injustice. A person who feels that he has a weak relationship with his / her manager may think that the manager discriminates and disrespects him / her in relation to him / her and eventually finds a more pessimistic attitude towards the organization. This chronic pessimism destroys organizational commitment and job satisfaction, marginalizes employee participation in organizational decisions, and on the other hand, citizenship behavior in the organization becomes a dream that will never be realized. As a result, such organizations face low staff performance (Mohammadian et al., 2018). One of the most significant changes in the world today is the shift from individual to team-based work. Teams have been considered as the basic units of organizations and key points to improve the performance of the organization. One of the things that management should pay attention to in the team building process is the stages of growth and development of a team. The growth and development of a team usually follows a step-by-step process, and most teams go through more or less the same steps. One of the most famous of these models is the four-stage Takman model (Ghodsi et al., 2017). Senior management teams of organizations as the main decision makers of companies play a key role in creating organizational ambiguity. Behavioral integration of senior management team, which reflects the collective interactions of senior management team members, facilitates the movement of organizations towards ambiguity and better performance (Moradi et al., 2016). Top-level theory shows that the senior management team has unique characteristics compared to other groups in the organization. The members of the senior management team are involved in the assigned duties and responsibilities and are independent as members of the decision-making team of the organization. Hambrick

argues that the senior management team process is distinct from group processes at the organizational and departmental levels; because members of the senior management team deal with a high level of work responsibilities related to the organization, communication with other senior managers and senior managers' interdependence in each other in senior decisions of the organization. They are individually as senior managers and independently as members of the organization's senior decision-making team. Also, a team is a small number of people with complementary skills who are committed to a common goal and after setting performance goals, try to achieve the mentioned goals (Rasouli et al., 2018). TMT is a knowledge-based management team that emphasizes the diversity and functional division of members (Budersen et al., 2002). Diversity of TMT members can improve company performance through knowledge exchange and collaboration in TMT (Boon et al., 2009). Given that the people who have the most impact on the CEO are its senior management team (TMT) members, we focus on the CEO-TMT interface as a prominent intervention mechanism. Although researchers such as Ansley et al. (2006) and Norouzi (2013) acknowledged the mediating role of learning and innovation in firm performance mechanisms; they ignored the important role of TMT knowledge management capabilities in the relationship between leadership behaviors. And the company's performance from the CEO's point of view, how to maximize the coordination and application of diverse knowledge of TMT members is the key to ensuring the company's efficient performance (Ren et al., 2020). On the other hand, when it comes to the relationship between leadership style and performance; we need to determine which task is intended. Sometimes we use job, organizational, individual, or all of these things as criteria. Many times leadership style is so related to our performance that it has a direct effect on performance, and sometimes leadership style has an indirect effect on performance, and this is important. Sometimes leadership style has a positive effect on performance and sometimes it has a negative effect on performance. Leadership style is usually such that sometimes it affects the performance of staff and faculty members and sometimes it shakes morale and reduces motivation, so leadership style should be such that it increases morale and motivation, efficiency and effectiveness and productivity. In relation to other leadership styles such as moral leadership style; It greatly affects individual performance and has a direct relationship, but it may also affect job performance. One dimension of intelligent leadership is emotional leadership. There is a gap in the discussion of emotional leadership, which means that leaders and managers who lead very little to the components of emotional leadership such as self-awareness, self-management, self-motivation, social awareness and to the development of society or staff, both faculty and non-faculty. They paid attention to the title of a living thing (Hong et al., 2012). The success of the organization in achieving the goals depends on how management practices and effective managerial leadership styles. This is true in all organizations, including academic centers (Shakur et al., 2009). A transactive memory system however is a team-level cognitive construct including heterogeneous but complementary knowledge embedded in team members (Wegner et al., 1985). CEO has the highest responsibility in delivering and strategizing for any organization including each section or division. At Universities, the job of CEO is mostly described as "RECTOR" and this study aims to answer this fundamental question: What is the effect of Rector's humble leadership behavior on university performance when we use "the role of TMTs' transactive memory system as mediator. With exemplary humble leadership and characteristics of the rector of the University of Georgia in Tbilisi, this research shall use this university as case study.

1. Background of the Research

Ren et al. (2020) examined the impact of the CEO's humble leadership behavior on the actual performance and sustainability of the organization. Based on leadership theory and upper-echelon theory, we build a research model of CEO's humble leadership behavior, top management team's (TMT's) transactive memory system, and start-up enterprise performance, as well as the moderating roles exerted by strategic flexibility. Further, to validate the hypothesis, 400 valid questionnaires are obtained. Based on those data, the empirical results show humility, as a virtue, not only can significantly and positively improve start-up firm performance but also can promote the firm's sustainable development in the long run by providing a trustworthiness climate for TMT members. Moreover, TMT's transactive memory systems play a partial mediating role in the relationship between CEO's humble leadership behavior and start-up enterprise performance. Meanwhile, strategic flexibility significantly and positively moderates the relationship between CEO's humble leadership behavior and startup entrepreneurial performance. Finally, the theoretical and practical implications are discussed, and directions for future research are proposed

Mohammadian et al. (2017) studied intra-organizational humility as a central competence in leadership of modern organizations. His study was conducted to understand the concept of humility in the content of the organization and management. So he used exploratory mixed approach and data foundation research strategy were used and to confirm its indicators, with a survey. He then interviewed 12 human resource managers working in the country's banks and the results modeled the phenomenon of organizational humility and was presented in following dimensions: cognitive, knowledge ontological, emotional, epistemological, and behavioral epistemology. 200 bank employees were surveyed and results analyzed and the validity of the tool

were tested and confirmed and it was proved that the phenomenon of humility is supported is needed in practice and managerial process, but epistemological and content barriers have prevented the maximum use of this competency.

Lee et al. (2017) studied the moderating role of senior management support on employee attitudes in response to human resource development efforts. Based on the survey data of Korea Human Capital Company panel, 3899 responses from 159 large companies were analyzed by adopting hierarchical multiple regression analysis and regression-based path analysis. The results showed that human resource management efforts positively affect organizational commitment through job satisfaction. In addition, job satisfaction had a moderating effect on the interaction of human resource efforts and senior management support on organizational commitment. Finally, senior management support modulates the relationship between human resource efforts and employee attitudes, so that increasing senior management support for human resource management efforts improves job satisfaction and organizational commitment of employees.

Pashazadeh et al. (2016) studied the new relationship between honest and humble approach of ethical leadership and organizational performance. The results of statistical data analysis showed the confirmation of the conceptual model and research hypotheses with high confidence. This means that the two methods of humble and honest leadership have a positive and significant relationship with organizational performance and social capital variable plays a mediating role in this regard. He showed that universities and other organizations can improve the organizational performance of employees by strengthening the skills of humble leadership and honest leadership in managers and supervisors of organizational units and also pay attention to the mediating role of social capital in the relationship between ethical leadership and organizational performance. It is important and significant.

2. Conceptual model/ research hypotheses

3.1 The main Hypothesis

Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance by mediating the role of Top Management Team (TMT)'s transactive memory system

3.2 Sub-hypotheses

A. Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on TMT's transactive memory system.

B. TMTs' transactive memory system has a positive impact on university performance.

C. Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance.

The Conceptual Model of Research:

3. Research Methods

The present study is an applied research and in terms of method is also descriptive-survey. The statistical population of this research is 250 staff of University of Georgia according to university internal database and the sample size is 148 according to Morgan table and sampling method is based on being a member of TMT (Top Management Team) that were including all division managers and school deans and faculty heads and programs and courses' heads. In this study, the required data were collected using a standard 15-item questionnaire. CVR test was used for validity and Cronbach's alpha method was used for reliability. The validity and reliability were .78 and .79 was obtained. Then k-s test as well as structural equations and path analysis with SMART PLS software were used.

4. Data analysis

•K-S TEST TO TEST RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H0 = Data distribution is normal

H1 = Data distribution is not normal

Table 1: Test of normality of research variables

Component	Sig	Result
University performance	0.016	Data distribution is not normal
Rector's humble leadership	0.014	Data distribution is not normal
(TMT)'s transactive memory	0.020	Data distribution is not normal

As can be seen in the table above, the significance level of all variables is less than 0.05, so with 95% confidence we can claim the rejection of H0 hypothesis. In other words, for all variables, the H0 hypothesis that the data is normal is rejected.

•STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS AND PATH ANALYSIS

The purpose of path analysis is to identify the causality (impact) between the variables of the conceptual model of research. It should be noted that the confirmation or rejection of hypotheses (relationships) is determined in a meaningful way. In other words, if the significance number is greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, the hypothesis is confirmed.

Figure 2: Structural equation modeling in standard estimation mode

Figure 3: Structural model in the case of significant coefficients

The path coefficient and t-statistic values indicate the intensity of impact and the significance of the relationship, respectively, and all research hypotheses have been confirmed. The results of the research sub-hypotheses are shown in the table below:

Table 2: Analysis of the relationship between research variables

<i>Hypothesis Path</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on TMT's transactive memory system	0.325	1.660	Rejected
TMTs' transactive memory system has a positive impact on university performance	0.517	3.887	Accepted
Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance	0.231	1.442	Rejected
Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance by mediating the role of Top Management Team (TMT)'s transactive memory system	0.1680	5.547	Accepted

Conclusion

In this study, four hypotheses (One main and three subalters) were examined. Two hypotheses were confirmed and two hypotheses were rejected. The results showed Rector's humble leadership behavior has not a positive impact on TMT's transactive memory system and university performance directly but TMTs' transactive memory system has a positive impact on university performance and by mediating the role of Top Management Team (TMT)'s transactive memory system: Rector's humble leadership behavior has a positive impact on university performance. The main research hypothesis of impact Rector's humble leadership behavior on university performance by mediating the role of Top Management Team (TMT)'s transactive memory system as a result is confirmed, but the beta statistics showed that the extent of this effect is very small, which indicates that this hypothesis is not so effective. In general, it can be said that the humility of the president of the university affects the performance of the university and can also promote the development of the university. However the cause of low effect can be attributed to the cultural and social structure of the study area that we have not surveyed those reasons and attributes. This is mainly because that humble boss can create a harmonious and calm environment, and he humbly leads more followers to strive to improve performance by creating a new shared vision. In addition, the humble university president creates an inclusive organizational learning atmosphere. These results are inconsistent with the research of Wren et al. (2020). The TMT interactive memory

system mediates the relationship between the humble leadership behavior of the rector and the performance of the university. This conclusion confirms that humble leadership as a "bottom-up" leadership style meets staff expectations of leaders in global culture, and that its characteristics bring psychological security to TMT members. In particular, first, this sense of mental security can enhance the understanding of TMT expertise in a variety of contexts and thus help TMT to integrate knowledge and experience in a variety of contexts, and ultimately strategic choices and decisions, adopt a better organization and improve the performance of the university. The psychological safety atmosphere conveyed to TMT by the humble leadership behavior of the rector of the University also encourages TMT members to new challenges. These concepts allocate more time and energy for cognitive resources, and thus university benefits more through team-based communication and information sharing, and largely avoid ignoring the market environment and related responses for and from competitors. Also, this climate is an important prerequisite for effectively promoting TMT to maintain efficient teamwork that could be very productive in Georgian working culture. The high degree of collaboration between TMT members facilitates the efficient integration of resources such as knowledge, skills and experience, thereby enhancing TMT's ability to respond to the business environment and ultimately achieves effective improvement in university performance. . In short, the CEO's humble leadership behavior improves the TMT interactive memory system by acknowledging its shortcomings, acknowledging employee value, teamwork effectiveness, and trusting subordinates. The TMT transactional memory system at universities can improve the composition, sharing and exchange of knowledge by enhancing Integrity and expertise-collaboration between members. All these achievements significantly improve organizational performance. In addition, staff participation is a central element in changing the mission, a university's sustainable survival strategy and converts values into measurable results.

From the above discussion, the rector of Georgian University can involve the TMT workforce in working together and turn the university survival and achievement of its mission into measurable results. These results are inconsistent with the research of Wren et al. (2020). In relation impact of TMTs' transactive memory system on university performance, we understand that due to increasing demand for making full use of members' knowledge diversity to enhance organization performance we need to gain shared-cognition among senior leadership in universities. This is very crucial outcome of this research. We proved that the transactive memory system of the TMT can effectively improve organizational performance too. Senior managers must be fully aware of the importance of building a transactive memory system for the TMT. It is clearly and particularly very important to strengthen the foundation of transactive memory systems of senior management teams for universities. With today's development of business globalization, TMT should balance and integrate the knowledge competition regarding knowledge diversity level. As the top leader, the CEO (At current case level the universities' presidents and rectors) should be more inclined to encourage executive team members to upgrade their specialization skills and cognitive style by exploratory learning and to share new knowledge with other team members timely due to increasing demand for making full use of members' knowledge diversity to enhance organization performance.

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